

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DETERMINING DETERMINING THE QUALITY OF THE GENERAL EDUCATION IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS INTERPRETATION OF PARAMETERS

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Abstract

The article first gives a scientific interpretation of the concept of "quality of education" and shows the main reasons why the quality of education is considered as an actual problem of society in the modern era. In the research work, based on the idea of "system analysis" (the idea of L. Bertalanfi) of the formation of the way of implementation of education resulting in quality results - the "system-structure" theory, which has become a development branch of dialectical philosophy, "compliance with the general laws of management and teaching-learning process" and "opportunity-movement" - new quality" paradigms, the idea of determining the adequacy of education to existing standards, norms, socio-economic requirements, the principle of conformity to the interests of the personality, society and the state" is put forward.

The article provides an interpretation of the parameters that determine the quality of the general education implementation process (by transforming them into the concept of "idea movement form of cognition") through the authors' personal experiences and generalizations on scientific research materials.

Keywords: quality in the field of education, effective management system, quality assessment methods, results of educational activity, systematic activity, cognitive component, reflexive component, regulatory component, communicative component.

Relevance of the research topic.

Education is such a system, process, value and result that most of its problems are eternal. This situation exists naturally (logically). Because education has an anthropological nature, its existence depends on the level of spiritual development of the objective reality determined by movement, time and space, and during the sharing of spiritual development, the functions of one of the main "enabling" components (educator) and the demand for the elevation of the other to the position of a creative personality are bound to change in a form corresponding to the evocations of industrial revolutions. Logically, the "Educational space" is subject to faster renewal according to the emergent calls of the techno-democratic-informational society. In spite of what has been said, the eternal problem of establishing an "optimal model" of quality education adequate to the contemporary demands for the development of education, including general education, and its management should be kept in focus. Among the cognitive issues aimed at solving this problem, the issue formulated as "Interpretation of the parameters determining the quality of the general education implementation process" has a special place. Therefore, we claim the relevance of the topic of the article.

Interpretation on the summation of research materials.

The problems of the development of education at the desired level and direction (adequate to the demands of modern times) affect everyone, from those who make management decisions on a national scale, to heads of educational institutions, scientific workers, authors of textbooks, methodologists, teachers, in short, those who organize the educational process at various

levels. and finally, it worries parents, the whole community, makes them think, and forces them to look for solutions. One of the problems related to the development of education, perhaps the first one, is the establishment of adequate quality education and its management. Professor R.H. Mammadzade rightly noted that quality management in education today is noteworthy for its relevance [6;3].

The generalization based on the materials of the scientific sources known to us can be formulated as follows: quality in the field of education means the level of learners corresponding to predetermined norms according to the results of education, and in general, the state of the education system. Quality is a philosophical category that expresses the certainty of any object, including education, and is an objective and general characteristic manifested in the set of its properties. Quality is a determinant of any process, thanks to which the process does not act like another process, but exactly that process and differs from other processes.

According to our understanding, the quality of the process determines the quality of the result in the process of education. "The quality of education can be formulated as the compliance of education with existing standards, norms, socio-economic needs, interests of the individual, society and the state". By the way, let's emphasize that "quality" has a special place among the "main principles of state policy in the field of education in the Republic of Azerbaijan". These principles include: humanism; democracy; equality; nationality and secularism; quality; efficiency; continuity; unity; permanence; succession; liberalization; integration. There is no doubt that it is based on these principles that the

main goal of education in Azerbaijan is realized. [4; 266].

Historically, qualitative (descriptive) methods such as the following were used to evaluate the result and quality of education in educational institutions: obtaining a forecast determined by teachers; assessment of students' morals in extreme situations that always occur in a student's life; assessment of students' morals in diagnostic situations thought and organized by teachers; evaluation of results according to the scale of criteria developed by the school itself; assessment of psychological indicators, all kinds of actions and activities used in the student's life: knows how to do (intellectual indicator); able to carry out (voluntary indicator); wants to relate (emotional indicator).[5;12-13]

After the restoration of our State Independence in Azerbaijan, the attitude towards improving the quality of our education and working out the scientific basis of its efficient management models has changed, and the work in the mentioned direction has become more constructive. "The modern concept of education considers the development of thinking as the main goal of the mental development of students" [1;54].

In modern times, the main reasons why the quality of education is perceived as an actual problem of society can be explained by two objective cases:

1) With the establishment of a quality education system, all subjects of educational activity - students, parents, one of the main components in the process of sharing human experience - education (in our modern times, it exists as natural and artificial intelligence that manifests itself as aspects of the unit), the effectiveness of the education system Managers and other employees at different levels are interested in its management. Recently, there has been increasing attention to building a quality education system for students. Both society and the state are very interested in providing quality education to citizens;

2) General education schools currently differ from each other due to the profiling of the training process, the application of innovative approaches, the effective use of new pedagogical and training technologies, the selection of new textbooks and teaching aids, educational programs, teaching-methodical complexes. The stabilizing role of the quality of education opens wide opportunities for effective management of the process in a situation where such diversity has become more widespread in the education system in recent years. Therefore, the tendency of parents and students to freely choose educational institutions is expanding, and the responsibility of educational institutions in preparing a competitive (continuation of competition) student and fulfilling the requirements is increasing.

Managing an educational institution (including a general educational institution) is a complex process. In that process, the evaluation of the quality of education is one of the leading directions of the mentioned complex process. In this management, it is possible to talk about effective management and its scientific bases if the process itself and its purposeful characteristics, the compatibility of the process parameters with the final result is ensured. Of course, the result depends on the process itself, its quality organization. In order to assess

the quality of education at each stage of the educational process from the point of view of management, grouping of its quality indicators, evaluation of educational results at periodic, near and distant time intervals during the course of the process should be provided, and the school's activities should be directed to these results. According to our subjective understanding, "educational quality management" should have a research character.

Scientific-pedagogical sources show that it is possible to group the pedagogical principles that ensure the effectiveness of quality management in education as follows: 1) The accuracy of information about the concept of "quality of education" as the main indicator of the efficiency of the managed system (if the managed object (system) is not clearly defined, then the meaning of management is lost, if the managed object is incompletely defined, then the management is ineffective, the educational system or education no positive progress is achieved in the activities of their enterprises); 2) Compliance of the effective management system of the quality of education with the general laws of management; 3) Correspondence of the effective management system of the quality of education to the laws and regulations of the teaching-learning process [12; 46-47]. Based on our generalizations to the research materials obtained from scientific sources, we come to the conclusion that one of the paradigms of the effective management system of the quality of education should be considered "the expectation of compliance of the administration and the teaching-learning process with the laws and regularities".

The quality level of education implementation depends on the form of its realization - the realization of the "opportunity-movement-new quality" paradigm.

In our opinion, the correct understanding of the concepts of "teaching" (this was interpreted as a way of implementation of education by researchers who are among classical pedagogues) and "teaching" activities, their functions, which are important elements of the categorical apparatus related to education substantially affects its correct implementation.

It should be remembered that the teaching activity is multifaceted. Although training is a characteristic of educational activity, it does not cover all aspects of it. Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. However, learning and learning activities are essentially different events. Appropriation is an integral part not only of the learning process, but of every field of activity, for example, play or work. Teaching activity is a type of activity, a unique form of social activity of the personality. In the structure of educational activity, its following components can be distinguished: 1) educational situation (or tasks); 2) educational operations; 3) control; 4) price [1;150]

Professor A.O. Mehrabov writes that the analysis of the approaches used to manage the quality of education leads to the following conclusions:

- in order to ensure quality management, the meaning of that concept must be defined in advance for each managed object;

- it should be taken into account that the quality of education includes common elements common to the entire educational system, as well as special elements that characterize each managed object and have a corresponding property;

- since the quality of education has a complex structure, and there is no unanimous opinion about its management methods, it is impossible to give its general definition and broad interpretation for any educational system and educational institution. [7, 214-215].

According to our subjective understanding, the "system-structure dialectical approach" should be focused here. When referring to such a methodological basis, it is taken into account that a part is a component that is part of the system and has relative independence. A system is complete, containing both elements and relationships between elements. The dialectical relationship of the whole and the part is actually the relationship that constitutes the structure of the whole, and in this sense, the structure acts as one of the important modes of existence of the whole. The dialectical unity of elements and structure is considered the main sign of the concept of system. The full concept is understood in terms of the system, it is the organization of the system. A system can be viewed as a whole consisting of the unity of its structure and functions. In principle, any system that has a higher, more complex completeness than the word enters another system as an element and a subsystem, and must obey its emergent sign.[3; 104-107]

The requirements of the specific consumer using the educational system determine the main content of the quality of education, which is directly related to the functioning of the educational system. All parameters of the activity are subject to these requirements. In many cases, the education system has to work with several consumers at the same time. In such cases, it is very important to fulfill the requirements of the consumer, which requirements to take as the basis for determining the quality of education. The conducted analyzes show that in such cases it is logical to fulfill the requirements of the graduates. It is this approach that meets the requirements of building student-oriented education. Here, in the norms and standards in force, a large number of requirements that have already received public and state status should be summarized. Students should be grouped according to the same or similar requirements. These requirements include a certain part of the quality of education and allow determining its content.

Many methods of quality assessment are used in education. These can include: 1) licensing of educational institutions; 2) attestation of teaching staff and educational institutions; 3) intermediate and final attestation of students; 4) audit of teaching and other activities of educational institutions; 5) professional, competitions related to professionalism [7; 216].

Among the presented issues, quality control in education and regular review of its status occupy a special place. In this case, the procedures for evaluating the quality of any process and determining new evaluation criteria for homogeneous objects are taken as the basis.

In the formation of the effective management system of the quality of education, it is of particular importance to give priority to the approaches related to management according to "process" or "result". In some approaches, it is suggested that it is possible to divide the processes taking place in educational institutions into three groups - basic, controlled and auxiliary. In our opinion, the group expressed by the concept of "basic" includes scientific-methodical and scientific-research works; strategic planning for management, evaluation of the level of use of the results of educational activities of consumers; and it is logical to include material provision, financial and infrastructure management to the auxiliary.

It is desirable that the results of the educational activity fully correspond to the requirements of the consumer. This is very important. The main issue here is to determine which results should be considered as the main indicator of educational activity. It is known that since the object of interaction in education is education, it is logically necessary to give the results of education in the characteristics that belong to the student.

Some researchers have determined the results of education with such approaches and based on the following: 1) students' knowledge, skills and habits; 2) indicators of the learner's personal development process; 3) developed effective approaches to eliminate negative effects affecting the teaching-learning process; 4) students' level of competence. Some researchers highlight the following as the results of education: 1) high self-awareness of the personality; 2) physical and mental health; 3) his high education, his need for education and his habits; 4) high education; 5) the position of patriotism and high patriotism. Another group of researchers, as the result of education, considers the level of education of those who have completed their education as the main indicator, which includes the following parameters: 1) knowledge, skills and habits; 2) level of culture; 3) spiritual development, value indicators; 4) the possibilities of intellectual and physical development of the organism.[4]

Researches show that the quality characteristics related to the subjects of educational activity play an important role in the modernization of education as a whole.

Circumstances related to the events occurring in the educational process create ample conditions to act as the main provider of the quality indicator of the teaching-learning process, while having appropriate effects on the participants of the process. Determining the quality of training depends on sanitary-hygienic, moral-psychological, resource provision conditions of the educational process and many other factors. Therefore, in the educational process, such factors should be determined with special approaches and the boundaries of their sphere of influence should be defined.

The characteristics that ensure the efficiency of quality management in education, more precisely, the compliance of the quality management system with the general laws of management, have been partially investigated [11].

The conducted analyzes show that the establishment of the education quality management system

without taking into account the laws of general management cannot ensure the efficiency of quality management. Such a conclusion is fully consistent with the "system-structure" approach [3; 104-107] and L. Bertalanfi's idea of system analysis [9; 8], which was formed as an important branch of dialectics.

In creating the methodological basis of the effective management system of the quality of education, an approach that ensures "systematic activity" should be used. In general, the structure of the education quality management system should consist of a dialectical sum of the managing and managed subsystems. Informational information comes from the management subsystem to the managed subsystem. The response to this information indicates changes in the managed subsystem. [4]

From the analysis, it can be concluded that in this case, the following cases may occur in the managed system that receives informational information:

- the quality of the managed subsystem's activity increases;
- there is no change in the operation of the managed subsystem;
- the quality of the managed subsystem's activity decreases.

The main condition for the effective management of the quality of education is the correct establishment of feedback between the managing and controlled subsystems. In this case, the following requirements must be met: completeness, appropriateness, adequacy, objectivity, convenience, continuity, structuring [13;34].

The structure of the administrative subsystem depends on the combination of factors that determine the meaning of the quality of education and includes the following:

- methods of evaluating the quality of education;
- the processes taking place in the educational system;
- subjects of educational activity;
- the results of educational activities;
- conditions in which educational activities are carried out [7; 218-219].

With regard to the managed object (system), subjects of management consistently perform certain management functions: targeted analysis; to plan; control; revision and reanalysis. Among the functions of training quality management, the importance of planning should be emphasized. The achievement of each goal (conclusion as a result) depends on the selection of the methods of its implementation, the determination of the steps of the deliberate implementation of the methods of ensuring the consistency of the process. In fact, planning, in a certain sense of the word, consists of forecasting, programming and working plan preparation [8;40]. Plan indicators enable control. If the planning is done correctly, management activities are properly directed, good results are achieved and time is saved. In the education system, stable conditions are needed to achieve the normal learning process of schools and the development of the school, to achieve quality in education. However, in real life, the internal and external environment of the school is constantly changing, some-

thing is happening in the lives of teachers, and children's attitudes towards life are changing. It is often impossible to foresee these changes. They either hinder the implementation of the plans or expand the opportunities to improve the quality of education. In well-organized management, these changes are detected in time and changes are made to plans and work done accordingly. The control system obtains information about these changes through well-organized control or periodic monitoring.

Management requires feedback. Management is impossible without it. If it is taken into account that the object of control is the quality of education, its importance increases even more. By the way, let's emphasize that there are many factors in the educational process and the quality of education can be improved due to them.

Achieving the quality of education, the structure of results-oriented management is formed from relevant operations. Here, the implementation of tasks and goals, the achievement of necessary results depends on the choice of management strategy. There are three main development strategies for the school to work in the innovation mode, adopt and apply innovations: local, modular, systemic [8;56-57]

The local strategy involves the use of various unrelated factors that will affect the quality of education. Such changes are carried out on the basis of independent plans and certain results are achieved. They affect the development and progress of the school.

A modular strategy is used in a class or at a certain stage of education in a complex manner of certain problems. In this case, the object of implementation of each idea is determined, the program of the experiment is prepared, its parameters are coordinated, applied, and the results are compared. If interesting results are obtained, it is studied and used. In this process, a team of like-minded and innovative teachers and managers to lead them are formed, which is of great importance in achieving quality.

The third strategy is the strategy of systemic changes. At this time, it is about the coordinated and planned implementation of all factors, innovations, and changes that can affect the final results in the management of the quality of education. The innovations applied here should be coordinated, and a development program of the educational institution should be prepared. The program for the reconstruction of systemic changes can be prepared when the school leaders are familiar with the application, organization, and experience of all pedagogical collective innovation processes, and master the methodology of conducting experiments. It should not be forgotten that the choice of strategy also depends on the nature, complexity, and volume of the innovations to be applied [8].

From the summation of research materials, it is concluded that the quality of education can be understood as a relationship between goals and results. In order to achieve high quality in education, although it is complex and difficult, the goal that can be optimally implemented must be defined. Then, in order to achieve that goal, the shortcomings encountered in the analysis process are investigated. The following factors can be

attributed to these shortcomings: outdated, suboptimal, educational and development technologies that do not benefit the content of education or have lost their importance, or weak involvement of students in the educational process, etc. After that, it is clarified under what conditions the defects that manifest themselves in the educational process have arisen. Mainly, the following can be attributed to them: shortcomings of scientific and methodical conditions; lack of high-level teaching staff; material and technical base does not meet the requirements; shortfalls in funding.

Ensuring quality in education and its effective management requires the application of new approaches to the content and methods of training in order to form new professional competencies in students. In this case, it is necessary to include the following components in the structure of professional competences: cognitive; regulator (director); communicative; individual(personal); reflexive (involuntary) [8].

The conducted analyzes show that the components of professional competencies are formed as a result of the influence of reflexive processes. Therefore, it is necessary to be able to distinguish the following forms of the involuntary component:

- retrospective (critical understanding of past experience);
- situational (real assessment of the current situation, situation);
- perspective (foreseeing the consequences of the action, choosing the perceived option of the optimal strategy of morality, behavioral norms, etc.).

Since these components open wide opportunities for the student to effectively implement reflexive processes and high reflexive self-organization, they should be taken into account in the educational process and the formation of such qualities should be ensured [7; 222].

Experience shows that it is important to ensure quality in education and put new approaches to its effective management in the foreground, not to allow mechanical transmission of ready-made knowledge, and to create appropriate conditions for the implementation of creative searches in the field of professionalism.

The quality of education is a category that changes from time to time, and it changes and updates according to the needs of social customers based on the context of our time. This reality requires that the monitoring of the results of education be carried out systematically, searches for quality improvement [12] be carried out.

Continuous, realistic, and relevant assessment and evaluation programs provide teachers and parents with evidence of each student's learning outcomes and successes. Such objective information allows students, teachers, and family members to accurately determine the educational goals of students and plan the next level of education. The scores collected by the students are not enough to evaluate their activities and to determine the extent to which the students have achieved their goals. Students should have the opportunity to set personal goals, monitor their own personal development and reflect on the knowledge, skills and attitudes they have achieved. The means of evaluating the learning success of students should also have a teaching function

and help them understand their learning outcomes. Inspection and evaluation criteria should assess students' learning activities both as a result of work and as a process itself, and should serve to reveal students' different and individual characteristics. Assessment should not serve to determine how one student reads in relation to another student, but should reveal the student's own level of individual development, while not referring to external motives [8].

It should not be forgotten that the assessment of student achievements is considered as a process of collecting information about the student's ability to acquire knowledge, use it, and draw conclusions, and serves the following purposes: 1) monitoring the student's progress (retardation); 2) making decisions in the training process; 3) evaluation of student's training results; 4) curriculum evaluation.

Assessment and learning processes are seen as two interacting aspects of education. Evaluation, which is a systematic process, is established by covering the following components as a means of effective feedback between training results and stakeholders: 1) Evaluation standards; 2) Data collection; 3) Assessment results; 4) Evaluation standards. [2; 294-295]

By the way, it should be emphasized that the following principles are followed in conducting all types of evaluations: expediency; mutual evaluation of achievements and educational opportunities; ensuring qualitative relevance and reliability of collected data, transparency, fairness, mutual agreement and cooperation in assessment; ensuring the developmental role of assessment results in training activities.

Monitoring and evaluation should be considered as the main tool for studying the quality of the pedagogical process and its individual areas. As in all management systems, in order to achieve the set goals in the training process, the process should be managed, evaluated at each stage, deviations should be noted, and clarifications should be made. At this time, the following requirements must be met: 1) the purpose of management must be clearly stated; 2) the starting state of the managed process should be noted; 3) the mechanism of influence on the process in the intended main transition states of the controlled process should be determined; 4) systematic feedback and the processing of the data received as a result of it should be ensured, a mechanism should be created to regulate deviations during data processing. [5;11-12]

In order to establish a quality teaching-learning process in our education system and its effective management, it is necessary to ensure the development of the scientific, pedagogical-psychological, methodical bases of new pedagogical technologies, interactive learning methods and their results in the pedagogical process.

The scientific-theoretical novelty of the work:

1) Improving the quality of general education, finding the management ways that determine the expected level is shown to be a socially significant objective of public importance; 2) The scientific interpretation of the concept of "quality of education" was given and the main reasons why the quality of education is perceived as an

actual problem of society in modern times were indicated; 3) "system analysis" of the formation of the way of implementation of education resulting in quality results is based on the "system-structure" theory, which has become a development branch of non-dialectical philosophy, "compliance with the general laws of management and teaching-learning process" and "opportunity-movement-new quality" paradigms, "the idea of determining the adequacy of education to the existing standards, norms, socio-economic requirements, the principle of conformity to the interests of the personality, society and the state" was put forward and interpretations were given on those parameters.

The result

The formation of the way of implementation of general education resulting in quality results is based on the idea of "system analysis" - the "system-structure" theory, which has become a development branch of dialectical philosophy, "compliance with the general laws of management and the teaching-learning process" and "opportunity-movement-new quality" paradigms, "The adequacy of education to the existing standards, norms, socio-economic requirements, the principle of compliance with the interests of the personality, society and the state is determined by the parameters.

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